

Welcome to:
University Teaching: Basics
**Unit 4: Teaching methods and
learning activities**

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Check-in

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Agenda

- Active learning
- Activating teaching methods
- Break around 17:30 (EET)
- Student motivation

Flashback: unit 2: Shift from teaching to learning

- 1990ies: influence of constructivist theory
- Learning as active / constructive process
- Instruction = guiding
- responsibility for learning process lies teachers **and** learners
- information linked to prior knowledge
- enhancement of self-organised and **learning**

Active learning - definitions

Def. 1: strategies that promote active learning as ‘instructional activities involving students in doing things and thinking about what they are doing’ Bonwell and Eison, 1991:

Def. 2: Active learning implies that students are engaged in their own learning. Active teaching strategies have students do something other than taking notes or following directions ... they participate in activities...[to] construct new knowledge and build new scientific skills”
(Handelsman et al., 2007)

Def. 3: “Active learning engages students in the process of learning through activities and/or discussion in class, as opposed to passively listening to an expert. It emphasizes higher-order thinking and often involves group work.” (Freeman et al., 2014)

Def. 4: “Students’ efforts to actively construct their knowledge.” (Carr et al. 2015)

Strategies that promote active learning ...

- ... Focus on activities that students do to construct knowledge and understanding
 - ... Require students to do something – read, discuss, write – that requires higher-order thinking
 - ... emphasis on metacognition—students' thinking about their own learning—providing the link between activity and learning.
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Special case: online-teaching and learning

- online-teaching is not face-to-face teaching transferred to the online-environment (ideally)
- Student activation is even more important (distraction, no physical cues, less ,social motivation‘)

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Do you think active learning methods are useful in all teaching settings / formats?

Teaching-style for centuries →

https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/b/b3/Faraday_Michael_Christmas_lecture.jpg

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Teaching methods, strategies, techniques

Teaching methodologies (also known as teaching methods/instructional strategies/techniques:) refer to a “set of practices and principles used by teachers to make the process of teaching and learning highly effective for their students.”
(<https://www.teachmint.com/glossary/t/teaching-methodologies/>)

Online learning tools refer to any program, app, or technology that can be accessed via an internet connection and enhance a teacher's ability to present information and a student's ability to access that information.
<https://study.com/academy/lesson/what-are-online-learning-tools-definition-types-examples.html>

Group discussion: helpful activation methods / strategies / techniques

- work in breakout-rooms for 20-25 minutes
 - What were the most helpful activation methods that you experienced so far (as student or lecturer)?
 - Explain the methods to your group and discuss.
 - Write down your favourite 2-3 methods in the etherpads (short explanation, use cases, challenges...) and prepare to present **1 of them** to everybody
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Group discussion: helpful activation methods / strategies / techniques – results from groupwork

Group 1:

Retrieval practice

Think-pair-share

Group Discussions (as teachers & students)

Concept Maps

Game Based Learning (May be not suitable for HE)

Give them a question and they discuss and use critical thinking to decide (One minute Paper)

Favourites:

1. One Minute Paper

The teacher gives them a question (picture, graph ...) and then students discuss based on what they learned

2. Group Discussions

3. Concept Maps

Group 2:

Group Projects: Students work on a piece of the web, the instructor explain the instruction and allow discussions.

Case Study: Oxygen Problem during Covid. Students were sent to the hospital to investigate the prob and try to solve it. study it clinically Causes, Symptoms, Treatment etc....

Miro: Using Miro (digital whiteboard): To promote asynchronous activities, before or after an online session. To help students prepare and benefit from synchronous sessions. To boost student participation in synchronous sessions.

Debate: Students are divided into groups but the groups' positions (against and for) are chosen by the teacher.

Flipgrid: It is a free digital tool where students can film themselves talking.

Favourites:

Case Study: Realistic and challenging. Covid might be a limitation to do it.

Group Project: it promotes active learning but it might some challenges when done online and sometimes one student does all the work.

Flipgrid: Both are very useful tools to be used for online learning because they motivate students and engage them. It might be difficult to use them in traditional classroom settings due to internet etc....

have a break, have a ... bongo cat

<https://bongo.cat/>

Motivation is the engine of learning

- Motivation can influence
 - What we learn, how we learn & when we choose to learn
 - → Motivation influences intensity, persistence and quality of the learning behaviours in which students engage
 - Motivated learners are more likely to
 - Undertake challenging activities
 - Be actively engaged
 - Enjoy and adopt a deep approach to learning
 - Exhibit enhanced performance, persistence and creativity
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What is motivation?

- “personal investment that an individual has in reaching a desired state or outcome” (Maehr & Meyer, 1997, in Ambrose 2015)
 - “a theoretical construct to explain the initiation, direction, intensity, persistence, and quality of behaviour, especially goal-directed behaviour” (Brophy 2010 in Hartnett 2016)
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Theories of Motivation

- Self-efficacy theory (Bandura)

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- Goal orientation theory (Murayama, Elliot, Friedman)

Created by Adrien Coquet
from the Noun Project

- Interest theory (Hidi, Renning, Krapp)

Created by Creative Stall

- Intrinsic-extrinsic motivation theory / self-determination theory (Ryan & Deci)

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Self-efficacy

- An individual's belief about their performance capabilities for a particular task within a particular context that has yet to be undertaken
- Self-efficacy is judged by
 - Actual Experiences (failures, successes)
 - Vicarious experiences (observation of others' success)
 - Attributions
 - Verbal persuasion
- Self-efficacy is a strong predictor of learning outcomes and satisfaction in learning

Goal orientation theory

- explores learners' reasons for engaging in achievement behaviour, in particular the beliefs that result in different approaches to and engagement in achievement situations (Murayama 2012 in Hartnett)
- Predominant types of goals:
 - Learning goals: focus on learning for understanding, competence development (internal standards)
 - Performance goals: focus on demonstrating competence (external standards) *OR* on avoiding appearance of incompetence
- → Ideal for motivation: ?

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 - Performance goals: focus on demonstrating competence (external standards) *OR* on avoiding appearance of incompetence
- → Ideal for motivation: combination of learning goals and performance goals BUT performance-avoidance orientation is negatively related to learning outcomes

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Goal orientation

- Goals are always present, often more than one
 - Conflict of teacher goals vs. learner goals:
 - e.g. learning goals vs. performance goals
 - some of lecturers' and learners' goals should align
 - Conflicting learner goals
 - Work-avoidance / understanding context / social goals
 - If more than one goal is satisfied – motivation is higher
 - Variables that influence which goal is pursued: value (importance), expectations to reach goal, effect of environment
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Interest

- a psychological state that “involves focused attention, increased cognitive functioning, persistence and affective involvement” (Hidi in Hartnett)
- content specific
- 1. individual interest: relatively stable motivational orientation towards certain activities
- 2. situational interest: engendered in response to particular conditions; less enduring
- → which one can we directly influence?

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Interest

- a psychological state that “involves focused attention, increased cognitive functioning, persistence and affective involvement” (Hidi in Hartnett)
 - content specific
 - 1. individual interest: relatively stable motivational orientation towards certain activities
 - 2. situational interest: engendered in response to particular conditions; less enduring
 - Situational interest can be triggered (e.g. with group work, use of technology) and maintained (e.g. through relevance, value)
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Intrinsic & extrinsic motivation

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- Intrinsic motivation: doing an activity for its inherent satisfactions rather than for some separable consequence (Ryan & Deci in Hartnett)
 - Extrinsic motivation: whenever an activity is done in order to attain some separable outcome (ibid.)
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Intrinsic & extrinsic motivation

- Connected to self-determination theory:
 - All humans have intrinsic need to be self-determining or **autonomous**, as well as **competent** and **connected**, in relation to their environment
- If environmental conditions support autonomy, competence and relatedness needs, then intrinsic motivation will be promoted (Ryan & Deci in Hartnett)

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- In what contexts did you learn sth. really well? (Well means: learned content and retained it for a long time or learned competences and got better at them.)
- What motivated you? Try to generalise from your individual experiences – what motivates for learning?
- Think for some minutes...

What can we do to foster student motivation?

How can we:

- foster self-efficacy?
 - Attent to students' goals?
 - Amplify interest?
 - reinforce intrinsic motivation?
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Things I am taking away with me...

Sources:

- <https://cft.vanderbilt.edu/guides-sub-pages/active-learning/#what>
 - Ambrose, Susan A., et al. *How learning works: Seven research-based principles for smart teaching*. John Wiley & Sons, 2010. (if you search for it on the net, you will find a free PDF online – it is worth reading!)
 - Hartnett, Maggie. *Motivation in Online Education*. Springer, Singapore, 2016
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